

Understanding Online Technology Attitude and Individual Teaching Efficiency of the Teachers

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Abstract. The current study evaluated the domains of online technology attitude that significantly influence the individual teaching efficiency of teachers. In this study, the researcher selected 215 elementary school teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected on the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Linear Regression Analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers, were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers. Linear regression analysis found that online technology attitude in terms of affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention are significant predictors of individual teaching efficiency of teachers. This was evident in the computed adjusted R² value of 0.698, indicating that it has contributed significantly to the variability of individual teaching efficiency of teachers by 69.80 percent from the total variability. This study provides a basis for developing policies and training programs that integrate online technology into teaching practices effectively.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational Management 2. Online Technology Attitude 3. Individual

Teaching Efficiency of Teachers

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1. Introduction

An educator serves as a role model of behavior that leads the learner towards successful direction and events in their academic life. Accordingly, demonstrating efficiency in work among teachers would also provide a clear image of a living example of the real essence of professionalism and integrity. The manner of teachers' delivery of lessons and the way they manage classroom situations are some of the factors that may contribute to the satisfaction of learning and development of the students. These are being evaluated periodically to gather some data and information that will serve as the basis for continuous improvement of the university. Thus, the administration and other sectors of the academe may improve the work performance

of the teachers by motivating them to perform their duties and responsibilities effectively and efficiently. As pointed out by Esen (2011), efficient teaching practices capture and maintain students' attention, fostering a positive and participatory learning environment. Efficient teachers can cover content effectively, ensuring that instructional time is used productively and that students have sufficient opportunities for learning. Likewise, Karatas and Gules (2010) expressed that efficient teaching involves adapting instruction to cater to various learning styles, abilities, and needs, promoting an inclusive and supportive learning environment. As noted by Hakanen and Roodt (2010), efficient teachers implement effective classroom management strategies, minimizing disruptions and creating an atmosphere conducive to learning. Likewise, Roorda et al. (2011) noted that efficient teaching practices include timely and constructive feedback and fair and accurate assessments, promoting student growth and understanding. On one hand, Mahajan (2016) asserted that the attitude of individuals toward online technology had a significant positive correlation with the method of teaching adopted by the teacher, the effectiveness of teaching, and the support provided by the teacher in learning. Accordingly, the difference was found on the basis of the teachers' own characteristics, like teaching strategies and self-confidence. Likewise, Tasir et al. (2012) noted that in these schools, which are facilitated with multimedia technology and worldwide networking, students learn in an individually-paced manner and include self-directed learning experiences (i.e., student-centered) and open-ended curriculum. On the other hand, previous studies indicated that there is a relationship between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency. However, those studies were conducted in foreign settings and utilized a quantitative approach. For instance, a correlational study conducted by Higgins et al. (2012) showed that there is a strong connection between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers, and studies have indicated a strong association. In addition, a descriptive quantitative study conducted by Hannagan (2010) suggested that efficiency in online technology usage utilizing communication can lead to a higher level of individual teaching efficiency among teachers. Also, Noor-Ul-Amin (2015) indicated that the positive attitude of the teachers towards online technology has the potential to innovate, accelerate, enrich, and deepen skills, motivate and engage students, to help relate school experience to work practices, create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, as well as strengthening teaching and helping schools change. As highlighted by Mun et al. (2013), poor individual teaching efficiency among educational service providers remains a concern that needs to be addressed among educational institutions worldwide. The report of Hales and Williamson (2010) claimed that teachers who are not enthusiastic about teaching were not able to create positive influence among other teachers that would further enhance their interest in teaching jobs. Nick (2012) indicates that teachers with poor individual teaching efficiency lead to the formation of unpleasant relationships with their pupils, and they tend to experience higher levels of emotional stress and burnout and a lower level of well-being. In addition, David et al. (2019) reported that the educational system in the Philippines is facing the reality of a productivity slowdown as a result of the declining work performance of employees. In the researchers' setting, it was found that because of poor individual teaching efficiency, learners are low-performing, as evidenced by the low General Scholastic Average (GSA) generated from all learning areas, which is perceived to be a product of low-performing educators. Also, it was observed that mediocre teaching efficiency among teachers not only provides the expected results, but their negative behavior distracts oth-

ers from doing their work and reduces organizational credibility. Lastly, due to the permanent nature of the job, they become less competitive in showing their capability to perform in school. It was also observed that most of the time they consume much of the principal's time and take the place of other workers who might be of more help to the organization. In this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Manay South District, Davao Oriental, using a mixed-methods approach. Specifically, the researcher used a sequential-explanatory design to understand the individual teaching efficiency better as determined by the online technology attitude, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding individual teaching efficiency in the context of teachers in the Manay South District, Davao Oriental. The results of this study may be of interest to other researchers as they could provide valuable knowledge for their research.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Online Technology Attitude*—Online technology attitude is defined as an individual's general evaluation or feeling towards computer technologies and related activities (Meel, 2016). Kutluca (2014) noted that attitudes are learned and can change with experience and social rules, affecting behavior towards computer technology. Mahajan (2016) reported a positive correlation between individuals' attitudes towards online technology and teaching methods, effectiveness, and support. Vaseghi et al. (2012) found that teachers with effective teaching styles and confidence had positive attitudes towards technology. The classroom environment, including satisfaction and support, predicts teachers' attitudes towards online technology (Sang et al., 2012).

Gilakjani and Leong (2012) emphasized that positive attitudes enhance the use of technologies in teaching-learning processes, while

negative attitudes hinder it. Abedalaziz et al. (2013) highlighted that ICT-mediated environments positively influence attitudes towards computer usage. Shaukenova (2016) and Amin (2014) noted that using online technologies helps teachers familiarize themselves with educational resources, leading to more positive attitudes. Wario (2014) concluded that actual experience with online technology develops positive attitudes. Samarkandi (2012) and Binder Niederle (2012) discussed the influence of computer-related attitudes on the desire to use online technologies and career choices.

1.1.2. *Affective Component*—The affective component of attitude is based on emotional experiences or preferences (Abdullah et al., 2015). Ali (2012) found that lack of online technologies in classrooms leads to unfamiliarity and low behavioral attitudes towards using them. Oye and Iahad (2013) confirmed that positive perceptions of e-learning are crucial for improving students' performances. Parker and Lenhart (2012) associated continuous e-learning use with increased academic performance. Lawton et al. (2012) and Conner et al. (2015) discussed how affective qualities guide intention and action, influencing behaviors and health-related actions (Bakr, 2012).

1.1.3. *Perceived Usefulness*—Perceived usefulness refers to the belief that using online technology enhances job performance (Sari-coban, 2013). Weng et al. (2018) described it as the perception of technology's ability to improve job performance, affecting technology acceptance. Briz-Ponce et al. (2017) noted that perceived usefulness is linked to positive performance outcomes. Suki and Suki (2011) and Hoffman et al. (2012) asserted that perceived usefulness influences the decision to use technology. Huprich (2016) highlighted that ease of use also impacts technology usage alongside usefulness.

1.1.4. *Perceived Control*—Perceived control is the confidence in one's ability to use on-

line technologies and handle problems (Saricoban, 2013). Aboshady et al. (2015) linked perceived control to positive outcomes through one's actions. Mahakalkar (2013) and Han et al. (2014) associated perceived control with well-being, stress coping, and improved performance. Suki Suki (2011) noted that low personal control can lead to apathy, affecting attempts to make positive changes.

1.1.5. Behavioral Intention—Behavioral intention refers to the interest in performing tasks involving online technology (Saricoban, 2013). Lu et al. (2017) and Sánchez-Prieto et al. (2017) linked involvement to participation in activities. Wang and Liu (2014) discussed the theory of planned behavior (TPB) and its accuracy in predicting health behaviors. Kurkinen (2014) suggested that perceived control enhances the predictive power of TPB.

1.1.6. Individual Teaching Efficiency—Individual teaching efficiency is the behavior relevant to organizational goals (Koopmans et al., 2014). Schaufeli and Salanova (2011) noted that teaching involves social engagement, leading to meaningful connections with students. Klassen et al. (2012) and Christian et al. (2011) highlighted the motivational aspects of teaching efficiency. Nick (2012) emphasized the collective nature of teaching efficiency, while Hakanen and Roodt (2010) discussed its impact on work engagement and well-being. Ahuja and Gupta (2018) linked teaching efficiency to long tenure and school culture. Amin et al. (2013) and Jalbani (2014) stressed the importance of effective teaching strategies in improving student outcomes.

1.1.7. Task Performance—Task performance refers to proficiency in job tasks (Koopmans et al., 2014). Gülbahar (2017) linked teaching efficiency to positive organizational behaviors and self-exploration. Clarke (2017) noted that teaching efficiency promotes proactive career behaviors, enhancing work readiness.

1.1.8. Contextual Performance—Contextual performance involves behaviors supporting the organizational environment (Koopmans et al., 2014). Boyd et al. (2011) and Rossi (2018) discussed the impact of working conditions and inter-organizational connections on teacher retention. Hodges (2015) and Herlambang (2013) emphasized the role of work ethic and discipline in performance.

1.1.9. Productive Work Behavior—Productive work behavior avoids harming the organization (Koopmans et al., 2014). Biggs et al. (2014) found that engaged workers maintain high work engagement even in undesirable conditions. This engagement translates to positive job outcomes (Kuok Taormina, 2017).

1.2. Synthesis—The literature in this study which is composed of theories and investigations has significantly assisted the researcher in establishing and positioning the context of the study. The study of Piccinini and Scarantino (2016) computation and information processes are among the most fundamental notions in that influence. Positive attitude towards online technology use encourage individuals to use online technology in completing tasks, thus, mediate cognitive processes. Meanwhile, Sansone et al. (2011) asserted that using online technology as cognitive tools in learning contexts, teachers and computers can become intellectual partners in learning; in the process, it helps teachers to surpass the limitations of their (commonly very limited) cognitive capabilities such as memory, thinking and problem solving capabilities, and to transfer some of the low level tasks such as calculations, storage and information retrieval to the online technology. Moreover, Liu et al. (2012) expressed that the use of technology increases achievement and self-efficacy. Accordingly, online technology, being laptops or computers, as noted by Al-Bataineh, Al-Bataineh and Harris (2016) are seen as tools and not replacements of best practices for teaching in the classroom. Another important compo-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ment of online technology is teacher efficiency. The teacher in the classroom must understand how and why teachers are efficient in teaching. Therefore, the researcher has played a crucial role in establishing the conceptual framework of the study. This involved explicit discussions on the nature of variables, the choice of population, and the method to answer the research objectives identified. The researcher's active involvement in this process has provided a solid basis for the interpretation of data. Furthermore, the literature reviews indicate that there are limited subcategories of school climate that are indisputably associated with the teacher's innovativeness in teaching, particularly for the teachers in rural areas who are newly hired and deprived from technological advantages.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework— This study was anchored on the proposition of Roth (2013) that situated cognition theory emphasizes that through the use of online technology as a tool in teaching, students develop motivated strategies for learning, leading to more efficient teaching performance of the teachers. Thus, in a computer-mediated classroom, members share and contribute information on topics of interest and assist members in basic communication activities. Computers may be used to record experts' clarifications and their answers to questions as the work is demonstrated and explained. Figure 1 presents the study's conceptual framework, which helped the researcher

summarize and briefly state the concept of the study. The independent variable is the online technology attitude or the individual's general evaluation or feeling of antipathy towards computer technology and specific computer-related activities. According to Saricoban (2013), the measures of online technology attitude are the affective component or feeling that a computer is manageable to utilize in learning processes, perceived usefulness or the degree to which an individual believes that using a computer would enhance his or her job performance; perceived control refers or confidence that they have have knowledge of how to use computers and they can manage to address problems that may occur while using it; and behavioral intention which refers to the interest of the student to perform tasks when they know that it involves computer. The dependent variable of the study was the individual teaching efficiency of the teachers or the actions of teachers relevant to the organization's goals. According to Koopmans et al. (2014), the measures of individual work performance are task performance, or the proficiency with which one performs central job tasks; contextual performance, or the individual behaviors that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function; and productive work performance, or the behavior that does not harm the well-being of the organization.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary objective of this study was to determine which domain of online technology attitude significantly influences the individual teaching efficiency of the teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. The research questions underlying the investigation in this study are as follows:

- (1) What is the extent of the online technology attitude of the teachers in terms of:
 - (1) affective component;
 - (2) perceived usefulness;
 - (3) perceived control; and
 - (4) behavioral Intention?
- (2) What is the extent of individual teaching efficiency of the teachers in terms of:
 - (1) task performance;
 - (2) contextual performance; and
 - (3) productive work performance?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' attitude toward online technology and individual teaching efficiency in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental?
- (4) Which domain of online technology attitude significantly influences the teachers' individual teaching efficiency in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental?

1.5. Hypothesis—The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance: H01 There is no significant relationship between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of the teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. H02 None of the domains of online technology attitude significantly influence the individual teaching efficiency of the teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. This study could benefit identified groups and individuals of the academe in the Philippines. This includes: Department of Education. Insights from the study can inform the development of policies that support the integration of online technology in education and enhance teaching efficiency. The Department of Education can allocate resources strategically, investing in technology training programs and infrastructure that address teachers' needs identified in the study. School Principals. School principals can create personalized professional development plans based on teachers' attitudes towards online technology, addressing specific areas that impact individual teaching efficiency. More so, principals could provide targeted support and resources to teachers, fostering a positive attitude towards online technology and creating an environment conducive to efficient teaching. Elementary School Teachers. This research could be important to elementary teachers because it could help them understand the dimensions that influence teachers' attitudes towards the use of online technology as a means for effective development of teachers' teaching efficiency that would prepare teachers to face the challenges in the information age. A positive attitude improves the accessibility of online technologies because the teachers sought to use computers where they are available. This could help teachers to realize the instructional possibilities afforded by computer technology. Teachers could learn to value past teaching experiences while identifying and maintaining the exploration of new technologies such as the computer. Future Researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the results of this study because the findings may provide a framework and model for future research in the context of online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency. For a

more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Online Technology Attitude. This was characterized as teachers' general evaluation or feeling of antipathy towards computer technology and specific computer-related activities. This study refers to the independent variable being described in terms of affective component, perceived useful-

ness, perceived control, and behavioral Intention. Individual Teaching Efficiency. This was conceptualized as the actions of teachers that are relevant to the organization's goals. In this study, the dependent variable was described in terms of the following indicators: task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative research, as described by Bhandari (2020), stressed that a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying was formed from a deductive approach where emphasis was placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while non-experimental research was research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, descriptive-correlational research, according to Myers and Well (2013), examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher was able to look into the relationship between two variables—online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of the teachers. In this connection, the study focused on exploring which domains of the online technology attitude significantly influence the individual teaching efficiency of the teachers. In this study, the use of descriptive-

correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to perform an experiment in a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the elementary school teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. In this study, the 215 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata were formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The inclusion criteria are as follows: teachers with two years of teaching experience; teachers with a certain level of technological proficiency or experience in using online tools; teachers who have access

to reliable online resources; and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and, thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—In order to gather the data, two adapted survey questionnaires were used. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments. The first part is about

the online technology attitude of elementary teachers adapted from the study of Saricoban (2013), which was divided into the following indicators: affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention. The Cronbach alpha value for this instrument is 0.918, which is described as excellent, denoting the high reliability of the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items were modified so that they may suit the context of this answer and be answerable using the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of the online technology attitude of the teachers, the researcher used the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations presented below.

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The online technology attitude of teachers is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The online technology attitude of teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The online technology attitude of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The online technology attitude of teachers is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The online technology attitude of teachers is never observed.

The second part of the instrument concerns individual teaching efficiency adapted from the study of Koopmans et al. (2014), which consists of 21 statements and was divided into indicators of task performance, contextual performance, and productive work performance. The Cronbach alpha value for this instrument was 0.911, which was described as excellent, denoting the

high reliability of the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items were modified so that they may suit the context of this study. As a guide in determining the extent of individual teaching efficiency, the researcher used a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. The Dean’s endorsement letter was attached to the permission letters

to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. The researcher submitted letters asking principals permission to conduct the study at the end of the second quarter for S.Y. 2022-2023. However, due to the busy schedule, four principals’ approval to conduct the study was granted in the

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first week of March 2023. Since those schools had sufficient respondents, the researcher distributed the questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after the study was approved. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The study was done in the fourth quarter of the school year 2022-2023 to administer the questionnaire. More so, the study respondents were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly

informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were provided to help them better understand the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, the researcher did not force them. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the individual teaching efficiency of the teachers as determined by online technology attitude and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents are teachers, so they are not considered vulnerable since all of them are of legal age and are not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real information source, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to

ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the data on the survey. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the natural source of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and adequately the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the study respondents—anybody with the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher made sure to respect the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier and sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication concerning the research was done honestly and fairly. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that the responses of the respondents were not influenced by any other factor like the conflict of interest. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the During the study, the Division of Davao Oriental was given a furnished copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials that were ample and available in the study. This was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by properly encoding the ratings of the

respondents during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every phase of research, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers; the significant relationship between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental; and the domains of online technology attitude that significantly influence the individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental.

3.1. *Online Technology Attitude of Teachers*—

3.1.1. *Affective Component*—Online technology attitude in terms of affective is described as extensive with a category mean of 3.75 and interpreted as the domain of online technology attitude is oftentimes observed among the teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. The mean rating of the different items ranges from

The extensive rating on the affective component denotes that the emotional and evaluative responses they have towards using technology in their teaching practices are oftentimes observed by the teachers. This finding is congru-

in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' online teaching attitude and individual teaching efficiency. It was also used to supply the answers for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (online teaching attitude) and dependent (individual teaching efficiency). It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by r . Multiple linear regression analysis was applied to evaluate the significance of which domains of the independent (online teaching attitude) variable significantly influence the dependent (individual teaching efficiency) variable.

2.54 to 4.29. The item, Feeling apprehensive about using a computer, reflects a mean rating of 2.54, described as less extensive, and interpreted as an item that is seldom observed by the teachers. Furthermore, the item Not hesitating to use a computer when I need to because I know how to use it has a mean rating of 4.29, described as very extensive, interpreted as item always observed.

ent to the view of Abdullah et al. (2015) that teachers with a high level of affective attitude enthusiastically integrate technology, creating engaging and dynamic lessons that captivate students' interest. This also agrees with the

Table 1. Online Technology Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Affective Component

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Being confident that I can handle computer without damaging it.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
2. Not hesitating to use a computer when I need to because I know how to use it.	4.29	Very Extensive
3. Feeling apprehensive about using a computer.	2.54	Less Extensive
4. Being comfortable in using computers.	4.11	Extensive
5. Using a computer does not scare me at all.	4.18	Extensive
6. Not hesitating to use a computer in because I look smart and intelligent.	4.16	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.75	Extensive

assertion of Al Bataineh and Anderson (2015) that teachers with a strong affective component exhibit positive emotions, contributing to a positive classroom atmosphere and fostering a conducive learning environment.

3.1.2. *Perceived Usefulness*—This dimension has a category mean of 3.28, which is moderately extensive, which means that this particular domain of online technology attitude of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental is sometimes observed. Adding on, the mean rat-

ings of the different items range from 2.44 to 3.90. Specifically, the item Computers make it possible to work more productively shows a mean rating of 2.44, described as less extensive, interpreted as an item seldom manifested. The item, Computers allow me to do more interesting and imaginative work reflects a mean rating of 3.90 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental.

Table 2. Online Technology Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Perceived Usefulness

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Computers help me improve my work better.	3.46	Extensive
2. Computers make it possible to work more productively.	2.44	Less Extensive
3. Computers allow me to do more interesting and imaginative work.	3.90	Extensive
4. Most things that a computer can be used for I can do just as well myself.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
5. Computers can enhance the presentation of my work to a degree which justifies the extra work.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

The result denotes that teachers’ belief in the practical benefits and advantages of using technology in their teaching practices is occasional observed. This finding supports the assertion of Weng et al. (2018) that teachers with moderate levels of perceived usefulness assess and choose technologies based on specific teaching needs, gradually incorporating them into relevant aspects of their instruction Moderately positive perceived usefulness leads teachers to integrate technology purposefully, aligning it with specific lesson goals to enhance student understanding. Likewise, the result agrees with the view of Suki and Suki (2011) that teach-

ers with moderate perceived usefulness strike a balance, leveraging technology where it enhances teaching efficiency without completely replacing traditional methods.

3.1.3. *Perceived Control*—This particular domain of online technology attitude in Manay District, Davao Oriental reflects an extensive category mean of 3.67 which means that it is oftentimes observed by the teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.67 to 4.38. The table further reveals that the item Knowing how to solve them one-way or another if I get problems using the computer has a mean

rating of 2.67, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item is seldom observed. Meanwhile, the item, Making the computer do what I want it to reflects a mean rating of 4.38, described as very extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested.

Table 3. Online Technology Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Perceived Control

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Being able to teach myself most of the things I need to know about computers.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
2. Making the computer do what I want it to.	4.38	Very Extensive
3. Knowing how to solve them one-way or another if I get problems using the computer.	2.67	Less Extensive
4. Being in complete control when I use a computer.	3.99	Extensive
5. Being able to use a computer all by myself.	3.77	Extensive
6. Not needing someone to tell me the best way to use a computer.	4.05	Extensive
Mean	3.67	Extensive

The result implies that the extent to which teachers believe they have control and mastery over the use of technology in their teaching practices is oftentimes observed. This result supports the findings of Aboshady et al. (2015) that teachers with a high perceived control exhibit confidence in troubleshooting, enabling them to address issues efficiently and maintain the flow of instructional activities. Also, this finding supports the idea of Han et al. (2014) that teachers with high perceived control feel confident to experiment with novel uses of technology, leading to innovative teaching practices that engage and captivate students. High perceived control empowers teachers to independently explore and integrate diverse online tools, tailoring technology use to their instructional preferences and

needs.

3.1.4. Behavioral Intention—Likewise, regarding the dimension of behavioral intention, it reflects a category mean of 2.95, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. The mean ratings of the different items range from 2.09 to 3.58. Specifically, the item Grabbing opportunity that I can come in contact with computers at school has a mean rating of 2.09, described as less extensive, interpreted as an item rarely manifested by the respondents. The item, Using Computers regularly throughout School, reflects a mean of 3.58, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed by the teachers.

Table 4. Online Technology Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Behavioral Intention

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Taking a task if I know it involves working with computers.	3.03	Moderately Extensive
2. Grabbing the opportunity that I can come in contact with computers at school.	2.09	Less Extensive
3. Using computers at school when it is necessary for teaching and completing tasks.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
4. Using computers regularly throughout school.	3.58	Extensive
Overall Mean	2.95	Moderately Extensive

The moderate extensive rating on behavior intention denotes that teachers’ plan or readiness to engage in behaviors related to integrating technology into their instructional methods

is sometimes observed in Manay District, Davao Oriental. This finding supports the assertion of Lu et al. (2017) that teachers with moderate behavioral intention choose to adopt technology

selectively, integrating it into specific aspects of their teaching where they see practical benefits. Moderately positive behavioral intention leads teachers to explore technology integration, trying out new tools and methods in a controlled and intentional manner.

3.1.5. *Summary of Online Technology Attitude of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental*—Overall, Table 5 shows the extent of the attitude of teachers toward online technology in Manay District, Davao Oriental. The overall

mean of the online technology attitude of teachers is 3.41, described as extensive, denoting that it is oftentimes observed by the teachers. Also, it could be seen in the table that the online technology attitude of teachers in terms of affective component acquired the highest mean score of 3.75, described as extensive. In contrast, the online technology attitude of teachers in terms of behavioral intention got the highest mean score of 2.95, which is moderately extensive.

Table 5. Summary of Online Technology Attitude of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Affective Component	3.75	Extensive
Perceived Usefulness	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Perceived Control	3.67	Extensive
Behavioral Intention	2.95	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.41	Extensive

The extensive rating on the online technology attitude of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, implies that interaction with computer hardware, computer software, other persons relating to computers, and activities that involve computer use is oftentimes observed. This finding agrees with Gilakjani and Leong’s (2012) assertion that positive attitudes toward computer integration enhance learning to use technologies in teaching-learning processes, and negative attitudes constrain it. Likewise, the result is in agreement with the idea of Shaukenova (2016) that the use of online technologies and other ICT related devices improves the positive attitude of the teacher towards computers because it help organize the teachers by helping them to gain thoughtful understanding and to familiarize themselves with several educational resources, approaches to evaluating

and providing solutions to problems through research works, philosophies, creative activities, and tests.

3.1.6. *The Extent of Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in terms of Task Performance*—Table 6 shows that this particular domain of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, was assessed by the teachers as extensive with a category mean of 3.40, interpreted as oftentimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.54 to 4.57. On the one hand, the item, Feeling full of positive energy has a mean rating of 2.54, is described as moderately extensive, and is interpreted as an item sometimes manifested by the teachers. Meanwhile, 6. I can perform my work well with minimal time and effort, reflecting a mean of 4.57, described as extensive and interpreted as always

manifested. The extensive rating in this domain implies that teachers' ability to effectively and competently carry out various tasks related to teaching responsibilities in Manay District, Davao Oriental, is oftentimes manifested by the teachers. The findings are congruent with the view of Kuok and Taormina (2017) that teachers with high levels of individual teaching efficiency excel in crafting well-organized and purposeful lesson plans, optimizing instruc-

tional time and student engagement. This also agrees with the view of Okay-Somerville and Scholarios (2017) that highly efficient teachers demonstrate dynamic classroom management skills, creating a learning environment that promotes active participation, collaboration, and positive behavior—employing effective strategies for maintaining a positive and conducive classroom environment.

Table 6. Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Terms of Task Performance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Managing to plan my work so that it was done on time.	2.56	Less Extensive
2. My planning was optional.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
3. Keeping in mind the results that I had noticed achieve in my work.	4.29	Very Extensive
4. Feeling full of positive energy.	2.54	Less Extensive
5. Knowing how to set the right priorities.	3.97	Extensive
6. I can perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	4.57	Very Extensive
7. Collaboration with others was very productive.	2.65	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.40	Extensive

3.1.7. *Contextual Performance*—In terms of contextual performance, Table 7 shows a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.25, which means that this domain of individual teacher efficiency is sometimes manifested in Manay District, Davao Oriental. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.44 to 3.90. Regarding item no. 2, I started new tasks myself when my old ones were finished, reflect-

ing a mean rating of 2.44, which was described as less extensive and interpreted as seldom manifested. Meanwhile, the item Working at keeping my job skills up-to-date shows a rating of 3.90, described as extensive and interpreted as often manifested among the students. This suggests that teacher's ability to adapt, collaborate, and contribute effectively within the broader context of the educational environment is sometimes manifested by the teachers.

This finding supports the view of Rossi (2018) that teachers with moderate contextual performance actively contribute to collaborative planning efforts, sharing insights and resources but may not fully maximize collaborative opportunities. Engaging in collaborative lesson planning and resource sharing with colleagues. More so, this supports Herlambang's (2013) assertion that teachers with moderate contextual

performance contribute to extracurricular activities, supporting student engagement beyond the classroom but may not be highly involved.

3.1.8. *Productive Work Performance*—Specifically, examining the domain on productive work performance, results in Table 8 reveal that its category mean is 3.66, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain on individual teaching efficiency is oftentimes

Table 7. Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Terms of Contextual Performance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Taking extra responsibilities.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
2. I started new tasks myself when my old ones were finished.	2.44	Less Extensive
3. Taking on challenging work tasks when available.	3.59	Extensive
4. Working at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
5. Working at keeping my job skills up-to-date.	3.90	Extensive
6. Coming up with creative solutions to new problems.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
7. Looking for new challenges in my job.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.25	Moderately Extensive

manifested by the teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 2.67 to 4.38. It is noteworthy that the item, Speaking with colleagues about the positive aspects of my work, has a mean rating of 2.67, is described as moderately extensive, and is interpreted as an item that is seldom manifested. In contrast, item, Focusing on the positive aspects of a work situation, instead of on the negative aspects has a mean rating of 4.38, described as very extensive and interpreted as item always manifested by the teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental.

Table 8. Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Terms of Productive Work Performance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Avoiding complaints about unimportant matters at work.	4.08	Extensive
2. Avoid making problems more excellent than they were at work.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
3. Focusing on the positive aspects of a work situation instead of the negative ones.	4.38	Very Extensive
4. Speaking with colleagues about the positive aspects of my work.	2.67	Moderately Extensive
5. Speaking with people from outside the organization about the positive aspects of my work.	3.99	Extensive
6. Doing more than was expected of me.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
7. Managing to finish the tasks ahead of time.	4.05	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.66	Extensive

The result implies that teachers’ ability to effectively and efficiently carry out their primary teaching responsibilities and tasks, achieving high levels of productivity in instructional delivery, assessment, classroom management, and related activities, is oftentimes manifested. This finding supports the view of Biggs et al. (2014) that teachers with highly productive work performance optimize lesson planning, ensuring that lessons are well-structured, aligned with learning objectives, and conducive to student engagement. Highly efficient teachers maintain

a well-managed classroom, creating an environment conducive to learning and minimizing distractions.

3.1.9. *Summary of Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental*—Lastly, Table 9 summarizes the extent of teachers’ individual teaching efficiency in Manay District, Davao Oriental. As shown in the table, the individual teaching efficiency of teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.44, descriptively rated as extensive. Adding more, results on the table shows that individual

teaching efficiency of teachers in terms of productive work performance got the highest mean score of 3.66 descriptively rated as extensive, while, individual teaching efficiency of teachers in terms of contextual performance got the lowest mean score of 3.25 descriptively rated as moderately extensive.

Table 9. Summary of Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Task Performance	3.40	Extensive
Contextual Performance	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Productive Work Performance	3.66	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.44	Extensive

The extensive rating on individual teaching efficiency of teachers implies that teachers’ ability to effectively and optimally perform their teaching duties, demonstrating a high level of competency, organization, and effectiveness in various aspects of their professional responsibilities, is oftentimes manifested in Manay District, Davao Oriental. This finding is congruent to the Esen’s (2011) claims that teachers with high individual teaching efficiency produce exemplary lesson plans that cater to diverse learning needs, maximize instructional time, and promote active student participation. Adding more, the result supports Balakrishnan et al. (2013) views that highly efficient teachers seamlessly adapt their instruction to address the unique needs of each student, promoting inclusivity and differentiated learning experiences.

3.1.10. Relationship Between Online Technology Attitude and Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental—The results of the analysis of the relationship between online technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between on-

line technology attitude and individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. Table 10 shows that online technology attitude has a significant positive relationship with the individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.334, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of online technology attitude changes, individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental also significantly changes. Moreover, the table also shows that the online technology attitude in terms of affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention are significantly correlated with individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.600, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.398, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.550, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.403, p < 0.05$), respectively. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between knowledge regulation skills and individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental.

Table 10. Relationship Between Online Technology Attitude and Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental

Variables	Individual Teaching Efficiency	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Affective Component		0.600*	0.002	Significant	Reject H0
Perceived Usefulness		0.398*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Perceived Control		0.550*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Behavioral Intention		0.403*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Overall Online Technology Attitude		0.334*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

This implies that teachers with a positive attitude toward online technology are more likely to incorporate online resources into their lesson planning. This supports Higgins’ et al. (2012) proposition that positive online technology attitudes encourage teachers to integrate technology tools for student engagement and interaction. This can include using online platforms, collaborative tools, and interactive multimedia elements, fostering a more dynamic and participatory learning environment. Online technology can aid teachers in organizing and managing classroom tasks more efficiently. From digital grade books to communication platforms, technology can streamline administrative aspects, allowing teachers to focus more on instructional activities.

3.1.11. *Influence of Online Technology Attitude on the Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental*—The significance of the influence of online tech-

nology attitude on individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, was analyzed using regression analysis. Table 11 shows that when online technology attitude in terms of affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention are considered predictors of teachers’ individual teaching efficiency, the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 205.832 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that online technology attitude predicts the individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.698 indicates that online technology attitude has contributed significantly to the variability of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, by 69.80 percent of the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 30.20 percent was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

In addition, table shows that the domains of online technology attitude significantly influence the individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. This table also indicates that affective component, perceived control, and behavioral intention are significant when the predictors are considered. This means that the extent of individual teaching efficiency of teachers increases by 0.305, 0.176, and 0.357 for each unit of online tech-

nology attitude. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of online technology attitude significantly influence the individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. Affirming that individual teaching efficiency is a function of teachers’ online technology attitude, the results are in agreement with the computer attitude model (CA) of Saricoban (2013) that through the use of computers and the develop-

Table 11. Influence of Online Technology Attitude on the Individual Teaching Efficiency of Teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental

Online Technology Attitudes Domains	Individual Teaching Efficiency	B	Beta	S.E	p-value
Decisions					
Affective Component		0.305*	0.349	0.064	0.000
Reject H0					
Perceived Usefulness		0.051	0.049	0.088	0.515
Accept H0					
Perceived Control		0.176*	0.162	0.081	0.001
Reject H0					
Behavioral Intention		0.357*	0.411	0.082	0.002
Reject H0					
R²		= 0.698			
F-value		= 205.832*			
p-value		= 0.000			

*Significant @ p<0.05

ment of positive attitude towards online technology, individuals construct their knowledge and meaning from their experiences and that knowledge is gained from the active thinking and performance in an authentic setting.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were based on the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the domains of in-service training influencing the classroom management practices of the teachers utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-predictive technique. The researcher selected the 215 elementary school teachers in Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. On the one hand, the result of the descriptive analysis shows that the extent of the online technology attitude of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, has an overall mean of 3.41 with a descriptive rating of extensive. In contrast, the online technology attitude of teachers in terms of affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention obtained mean scores of 3.75, 3.28, 3.67, and 2.95, respectively. On the other hand, the extent of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, has an overall mean of 3.51 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, the individual teaching effi-

ciency of teachers in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior obtained mean scores of 3.40, 3.25, and 3.66, respectively. Meanwhile, results of Pearson Moment Product Correlation analysis showed that online technology attitude has a significant positive relationship with the individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.334$, $p < 0.05$). Moreover, regression analysis indicated that when online technology attitude in terms of affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention were considered as predictors of individual teaching efficiency of teachers, the model is significant, as evident in the F-value of 205.832 with $p < 0.05$. Also, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.698 indicates that online technology attitude has contributed significantly to the variability of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, by 69.80 percent of the total variability. Also, online technology attitudes in terms of affective component, perceived control, and behavioral intention are significant predictors of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The online technology attitude of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, was described as extensive. Online technology attitudes in terms of perceived usefulness and behavioral intention were rated as moderately extensive, while online technology attitudes of teachers in terms of affective component and perceived control were rated as extensive. The result leads to the implication that the interaction with computer hardware, computer software, other persons relating to computers, and activities that involve computer use was oftentimes observed. Individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental

was described as extensive. Individual teaching efficiency of teachers in terms of contextual performance was rated as moderately extensive. In contrast, individual teaching efficiency of teachers in terms of task performance and productive work performance were rated as extensive. The extensive rating on individual teaching efficiency of teachers implies that teachers' ability to effectively and optimally perform their teaching duties, demonstrating a high level of competency, organization, and effectiveness in various aspects of their professional responsibilities, was oftentimes manifested. Further, online technology attitude was found to be significantly correlated with individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. This indicates that as the extent of online technology attitude changes, individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, also significantly changes. This implies that teachers with a positive attitude toward online technology are likelier to incorporate online resources into their lesson planning. Furthermore, it was found that the model is significant when online technology attitude in terms of affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioral intention are considered as predictors of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental. Online technology attitudes of teachers in terms of affective component, perceived control, and behavioral intention are significant predictors of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: Teachers must be provided with intensive ICT-based training to equip them with knowledge of ICT and its utilization in language teaching. It was further suggested that school administrators and stakeholders may look for interventions to upgrade the school's ICT-based resources

for their optimum use in teaching and learning. Most importantly, a larger school-wide ICT development plan may be implemented to ensure coherence of ICT implementation in the teaching-learning activities. Further, support staff and support staff training would be essential, and they should be a part of the strategy being developed for educational systems development. This support would best allow teachers to integrate technology meaningfully at the classroom level. Furthermore, the researcher suggests that school heads may conduct performance reviews regularly. Performance is essential to measuring teachers' performance. Thus, schools should hold individual meetings to let them know where they excel and what areas they need to work on. Lastly, researchers may conduct further analysis on the factors that influence the individual teaching efficiency of teachers since the attitude toward online technology has contributed significantly to the variability of individual teaching efficiency of teachers in Manay District, Davao Oriental, by 69.80 percent from the total variability.

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